

Original Article

Misunderstandings, false myths and diagnostic approximations in proctology, with reporting of obsolete concepts and observations from a new point of view

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Introduction

The greatest ignorance in Medicine is probably in the field of anal diseases. The competence index of a Proctologist is inversely proportional to the number of times he repeats the term “hemorrhoids”.

The real hemorrhoidal plexuses (internal) are normal anatomical structures that play an important physiological role in perfecting continence in synergy with the sphincter system.

The so-called “hemorrhoids” represent a popular myth for patients and a serious educational gap in the training of the Doctor and the Surgeon.

In reality, “hemorrhoidal disease” represents a minimal percentage of rectal-anal pathology and the term is abused to indicate a wide range of pathological situations that include bleeding, pain, anal swelling and various growths: however, these are only symptoms, common to many other pathologies, but in low-level proctology they are all lumped together, invariably, with a phantom disease called “hemorrhoids”, giving up right from the start on trying to understand their origin and evolutionary path. “Hemorrhoids” are found more “in the mouth” (of patients) and “in the brain” (of Doctors), than in the place where they should really be, representing a social cognitive bias.

The causes of the numerous and varied anal problems must be carefully researched, both anatomical and physiopathological, to arrive at a precise diagnosis and consequently plan a correct therapy, always different for each patient who must be “tailored”.

The text will contain simple sentences that correspond to those generally used to communicate with patients and some of my personal explanatory quotes and aphorisms.

AIM, BACKGROUND AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary clarification

Diseases such as diabetes, inflammatory bowel diseases (Crohn's, Ulcerative Colitis), autoimmune connective tissue diseases (Lupus, Scleroderma, Arthritis or Ankylosing Spondylitis, etc.), coagulopathies, tumors, depressive syndrome, thyroid disease, severe spondylo-discarthrosis, neuropathies, etc., can be a direct and primary cause of anal problems or can constitute a contributory cause, exacerbate the symptoms or prevent healing; in these cases, the first measures to be taken are precisely those of correcting, controlling or attenuating the negative impact of these pathologies, always under the supervision of competent Specialists for each

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medical discipline involved.

The purpose of this article is not to teach Proctology: for that, we refer to academic treatises by various Authors from which it is possible to draw all the basic information on the subject, such as in the latest manual [1], edited by the Italian Unitary Society of Colon-Proctology (SIUCP).

This publication tends to point out and correct the ambiguities of a Proctology that is conceptually largely outdated and that needs to be re-evaluated from a completely different point of view that can push towards broader objectives and consequently better therapeutic results.

Difficulties in Proctological therapy

In all pathological situations, one should not focus on the presence of a symptom, be it bleeding, pain or swelling and even less should one seek its “resolution” with symptomatic therapies, especially if self-managed, copied from a friend or recommended by a Pharmacist without a medical prescription.

The real “solution” consists in making a correct diagnosis, understanding the basic causes of the symptom, analyzing the pathogenic mechanisms and, only then, in trying to correct the “primus movens”.

This is why we must avoid those who promise non-existent “safe” or “definitive” therapies and not trust practitioners who, in a complex field of health, give everyone the same unique treatment, the only one they know how to do or the one that “attracts the most” the naive or that makes their wallets bigger.

It is necessary to rely on trusted, competent, serious and honest Specialists, who aim at the well-being of the patient and not at improving their bank account.

There is a big difference between a Surgeon who performs proctological operations and a real Proctologist: the Surgeon observes the patient “at 90 degrees”, sees that he has “hemorrhoids” and tries to convince him that it is better to cut them as soon as possible.

The Proctologist, on the other hand, observes the problem at 360 degrees, tries to understand, starting from the identification of the causes, which disease is responsible for the disorders complained of by the patient and based on this chooses the most appropriate therapeutic strategy.

The Proctologist, therefore, does not neglect aspects concerning different fields such as Urology, Gynecology, Neurology, Endocrinology, Dermatology and Venereology (et al.), becoming, with time and experience, a Perineologist.

Furthermore, he does not forget the psychological aspects of diseases, knowing well the reciprocal interactions between "anus and psyche", also carefully evaluating the impact of the pathological condition on QoL (Quality of Life).

...and as far as possible, leaves the poor hemorrhoids alone, almost always "innocent".

The "real" proctological visit

A Proctological visit (not to be confused with a Surgical check of the anus) includes a 360° anamnestic collection with careful evaluation of previous visits and tests, in-depth analysis of the specific clinical history, accurate defecatory anamnestic history with Wexner-test (Constipation Score), complete clinical examination with inspection of the entire perineum, anal exploration, but also vaginal in women and prostatic in men, endoscopic examination with a rigid instrument (Ano-Proctoscopy), neuro-functional evaluation of the pudendal nerves and the sphincter system, drafting of the diagnosis (preliminary or definitive), planning of the subsequent diagnostic-therapeutic process, therapeutic indications with a broad and detailed interview on the possible surgical aspects, discussion on the best opportunities in relation to the clinical condition found, also considering the various alternatives and the individual needs of the patient, with a reasoned and "tailored" choice, different for each individual patient.

Anal and hemorrhoidal misunderstandings

The greatest difficulty in a Proctological Visit is making the patient understand that "he does not suffer from hemorrhoids", but that, like everyone who comes into the office, he has "anal problems" that must be sought, identified, understood and treated accordingly, starting from their causes and not from symptoms common to many diseases such as pain, bleeding or swelling.

Unfortunately, popular culture, the many clichés about "hemorrhoids" and the poor preparation that university studies, as they are structured, provide to the medical graduate and even to the surgery specialist, mean that the patient approaches the proctological visit with a basic preconception, that of "suffering from hemorrhoids" ... after all, what else could it be? ... in fact it can be many other things, starting with **painful pathologies** such as anal thrombosis (and not hemorrhoidal ...), sphincter spasms, proctalgia fugax, fissures, abscesses, fistulas, ... going on with **growths and swellings**, such as edematous skin-tag, condylomas, prolapsed polyps, tumors ... without forgetting **bleeding lesions** such as polyps (benign or malignant), erythematous and/or fissure-like dermatitis, nonspecific or specific proctitis (ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease), solitary ulcer of the rectum... and finally **rectal or anal cancer**... and these are just a few examples of what can be found in a patient who claims to "suffer from hemorrhoids".

But the strangest thing is that, after having made the diagnosis, after having established an adequate therapeutic strategy, after having repeatedly informed the patient about the causes and the consequent development of his morbid manifestations, after having resolved the problems with medical and/or surgical therapy, after a short time the patient calls and says..."good morning Doctor, I am the one you treated for hemorrhoids...", at which the poor Proctologist literally drops the arms (and other) to the floor.

But it doesn't end there... "hello Doctor, my friend gave me your number, the one you operated on for hemorrhoids (???) with the laser (?????????), I have the same problem and I would like to have the same procedure"...

(causes of depression for the Proctologist).

Modern pathogenetic theories

Fortunately pathogenetic theories have changed in recent decades and are mainly addressed to the presence of "prolapse" [2], and sphincter muscle hypertonicity [3], relegating the poor and mistreated hemorrhoids to a supporting role, innocent victims of much more serious pathological conditions.

The ass: this unknown

There is great ignorance about anorectal diseases, burdened by historical, inveterate preconceptions, so that all patients who enter a Proctology office are convinced that they already know what they are suffering from and directly ask for the treatment that they have thought up by themselves or with the help of relatives, acquaintances, various media including mainly the **Internet, where you can easily find "everything and the opposite of everything"** and where it is extremely dangerous to navigate between sites of reliable professionals and blogs of approximate characters, bordering on charlatanism and wild-west remedies that are excellent and effective for all diseases.

People come into the office reciting a standard script, starting with "**Doctor, I suffer from hemorrhoids, maybe fissures, and I would like to have the operation**" (as if there were only one operation or only the one that is in their mind): in fact, in my long career, I have been able to see that, most people, "**have hemorrhoids in their brain and not where they should be**".

The most "informed" also ask, with the air of those who have already understood everything in life, for a very specific operation, because it is definitive, minimally invasive, painless, etc... my answer is "**to solve diseases you have to go to Lourdes**" because doctors can only try to understand what the disease is in order to deal with it in the best possible way, but without any guarantee of being able to achieve the desired result.

The typical phrases then continue with a "**don't hurt me**" at the time of the visit, as if it were the doctor who causes pain and not the diseases.

It therefore takes a great deal of time and patience to explain that "**hemorrhoids, in themselves, are not a disease**"; that there is more than hemorrhoids in the anus, that people who are well do not go to the doctor and that people who are already ill bring their pain from home.

The most common anal pathological situations (among almost 200 possibilities of differential diagnosis) that patients (and unfortunately many doctors) indicate as "hemorrhoids", are represented summarily by fissures, polyps, bleeding lesions, abscesses, acute congestive crises (from childbirth or recurrent) and the skin-tags that derive from them, as well as by thrombosis (mainly of the anal margin and not "hemorrhoidal"), dermatitis (allergic, fungal, psoriatic and from abuse of creams for "hemorrhoids") and also by sexually transmitted diseases; finally by anal or lower rectal tumors, treated for years as "hemorrhoids" and which unfortunately arrive late to the diagnosis.

In addition to "hemorrhoids" also other pathological conditions are burdened by poor knowledge and nonchalance in the diagnosis; without going into the details (which would require extensive discussions), two significant examples are highlighted:

1- "Constipation": each patient (and also each doctor) has his own idea: I am constipated because I don't defecate every day, because I have hard stools, because "I have to strain hard", because in the family we are all constipated, etc.; in reality **there are precise points (such as the "Rome II criteria") to establish the presence and degree of constipation**, but naturally

these must be investigated and evaluated by a specialist who is particularly expert in the field of colon-procto-perineology, not by a generic Doctor or General Surgeon, let alone by the patient himself or his aunt!

The diagnoses can be multiple and complex (Obstructed Defecation Syndrome, Slow-transit, pelvic/perineal dyssynergia, sphincter motor incoordination, organic constipation secondary to tumors, postsurgical adhesions, mega-dolichocolon, inflammatory stenosis from Crohn's, tubercular, scleroderma, etc.); equally varied are the possibilities of choice of therapeutic combinations, from dietary, to pharmacological, to surgical, to physical and rehabilitative ones. In any case, **constipation is not, as one might think, a "curse" to be carried for life:** if one manages to recognize the causes, medical and surgical treatments of a certain effectiveness are possible, always to be evaluated carefully, with adequate instrumental study, with extensive explanations to the patient on indications and limits and above all with a lot of realism and a lot of caution.

2- "Colitis" (or irritable colon or spastic colitis, etc.): no one really knows what it is, not even the doctor who diagnosed it so casually, without performing any tests, often attributing it to "anxiety or stress".

Aside from the fact **that it is not an "irritable colon", but the "Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS)"** which involves the entire digestive tract and not just the last part (the colon), the real problem is that a possible IBS represents a **"diagnostic defeat", being a "diagnosis of exclusion"** that arises from the negativity of all the possible (and fundamental) tests performed up to that moment (minimum and mandatory at least Colonoscopy, chemical stool test and for parasites and eggs, Fecal Calprotectin, test for lactose and gluten intolerance) which do not indicate either a tumor pathology, or diverticular disease, or IBD (Inflammatory Bowel Disease) such as Ulcerative Colitis, Crohn's Disease, etc.), or any other detectable disease. **When the Doctor has not understood the real reasons for the abdominal and defecatory disorders of the patient in front of him, he gives up and pronounces IBS, vulgarly calling it "colitis or irritable colon".**

What is the reason for this ignorance and these widespread preconceptions?... simply because doctors, of all times, have never been deeply interested in anal diseases and that, with rare exceptions, until a few decades ago there were no specialists in Proctology in the world.

Anal surgery, for over 6500 years, that is, since the time of the ancient Egyptians, has not changed much from its basic approach, **calling "hemorrhoids" everything that protrudes from the anus and practicing its systematic destruction by any means** (knives, scissors, scalpels, strangling ligatures, red-hot irons... then with progress electricity, ice, infrared rays, ultrasound, radiofrequency and finally, the miraculous LASER (May the Force be with you): in fact, with the various destructive instruments, the same amputative procedure is always performed, painful, naive, often useless and a source of complications and relapses, called hemorrhoidectomy... **"change the spoon, but don't change the soup"**

Universities and the main Scientific Surgical Societies have often neglected to adequately educate their students on the social and individual importance of anal diseases, because the "school" traditions did not provide for such specific training, indeed, with contempt for those diseases considered to be of "low rank" the first operation entrusted to the young surgeon was the one of the "hemorrhoids" that involved "brutal tear" of various, poor, anal appendages not better identified, with a method rightly defined as **"Rottweiler Hemorrhoidectomy"**.

General Surgeons have never looked favorably on "Proctologists", considered presumptuous "robbers" of what the surgeons themselves believe, erroneously, to understand perfectly.

Anal rescue

More and more often, in the Specialized Proctology Centers (Colon-Proctology Unit), it happens that they have to evaluate patients who have already been operated on elsewhere, even several times for "hemorrhoids" that "grew back" (?) and with symptomatic problems never resolved (persistence), even worsened, who have presented the same disease again (recurrence), have had an adverse event directly or indirectly dependent on the surgery undergone (complication), have presented further pathological expressions (associated lesions).

CONCLUSIONS

Ultimately, the best indication for a patient suffering from anorectal and perineal diseases is to turn to a competent Procto-Perineologist Specialist with great experience (detectable from the professional Curriculum), master of all the main possible therapeutic techniques, with a large surgical case history, able to choose, for each individual patient, the best solution, based on the anatomical, physiological, pathological aspects specific to the clinical situation in question, on the physical and psychological characteristics of the patient and, last but not least, on the specific needs of the patient himself (family, relational, work, sports, psycho-social), in order to obtain the best possible therapeutic result.

There is only one anus and there is no "spare part" like for the heart, liver, kidneys or the muffler of a car: the anus must be treated with the utmost care from the first intervention, but, in case of failure, only an expert Proctologist will be able to save the anus (anal rescue).

Contrary to popular belief, hemorrhoids not only do not hurt, but they do not even represent a disease and in most cases, when they are involved in pathological processes, these depend on other pre-existing diseases (mainly rectal prolapse and sphincter hypertonicity): there are many other reasons for anal pain (fissures, fistulas, abscesses, infections, tumors, etc.) whose diagnosis must be precise in order to set up a correct therapy.

An initial intervention that is not indicated, forced or frankly wrong, not only will not lead to healing, but may also cause damage, requiring subsequent interventions, made more difficult by previous outcomes.

Beware of "do it yourself"

Self-managed therapies or those suggested by relatives and friends are a waste of time, often being useless and dangerous.

Too many rectal cancers are diagnosed late because they have been treated for years with "hemorrhoid creams": before any treatment, it is necessary to make the right diagnosis.

Advice for patients: For every pathological situation, there is a Specialist, don't give up on it! Don't do it alone!! Don't do the same as your neighbor! Don't listen to your aunt! Your problem is never the same as someone else's, so the treatment must also be different!

But above all, don't think you know your problem: that's the worst mistake.

Conflict of interest

Author declares that he has no conflicts of interest.

Research involving human participants and/or animals: this article does not contain any experimental study with human or animal subjects.

Informed consent

For this type of study consent is not required

REFERENCES

1. Renzi A.(2018) Chirurgia Colonproctologica e Pelviperineale. Ed. Piccin, Padova. ISBN 978-88-299-2883-5.
2. Longo A. (1998) Treatment of haemorrhoids disease by reduction of mucosa and haemorrhoidal prolapse with circular suturing device: a new procedure. 6th World Congress of Endoscopic Surgery. Rome.
3. Gallese N. (2021) Identification of a new syndrome: ASS-SSA or anal sphincter syndrome Ann. Ital. Chir. 92 2:180-182.

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